

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of attitude toward behavior on vasectomy contraception in men

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Abstract

The fast growth of population in Surabaya City is breeding numerous problems, starting from poverty all the way to an increase of crime rate. In mitigating those problems, the usage of contraception is one of the methods used to reduce the population density in Indonesia. This study aims to analyze the effect of attitude towards behavior on the usage of vasectomy contraception in men. This study uses observational analytic design. The approach used in this research is cross-sectional. Population for this study are men with more than three children that are domiciled in Putat Jaya, Kecamatan Sawahan, Surabaya. The variables in this study are independent and dependent variables. The independent variable is the attitude towards behavior and the dependent variable is the intention to use vasectomy contraception. The result of this study shows that there is a significant effect of attitude towards behavior on the intention to use vasectomy contraception. The p-value for the test is 0,002 ($<\alpha=0.05$) with the category of “supporting”. Therefore, from that result, we conclude that attitude towards behavior of “supporting” have an effect up to 33,3 more than “not supporting” behavior on the intention to use vasectomy contraception. In conclusion, attitude towards behavior have a significant effect on the intention to use vasectomy contraception.

Keywords: Attitude towards behavior; Family Planing; Vasectomy; Contraception; Population

1. Introduction

Indonesia is one of the countries with the most population. As of 2023, Indonesia holds the fourth position of the countries with most population in the world [1]. According to Worldometes report on January 31 2023, the population of Indonesia recorded are 273,52 million people[2]. The population growth in Indonesia keeps increasing every year. This is evident that in the year 2023, the population of Indonesia have reached 278,52 million people, from 275,77 million people in 2022[3]. The increase also happened to fertility rate, where Indonesia is the fifth country in the world with the most birth. Indonesia contributes 13,370 births, which placed Indonesia in the fifth position after India, China, Nigeria, and Pakistan[4].

Population density can cause numerous problems such as poverty, inadequate health service, the increase of unemployment rate, and the increase of crime rate. To cope with this problem, the government keep trying to suppress the population’s growth rate with a program called Program Keluarga Berencana (KB) or through the use of contraception[5]. The use of contraception is aimed to prevent pregnancy temporarily or permanently[6]. World Health Organization states that KB is one of the method that helps individual or couples to reach certain objective, preventing unwanted pregnancy, setting the interval between pregnancies, controlling the time of birth, and deciding the number of children in a family[7].

Keluarga Berencana is one of the method used to decrease the maternal mortality rate from year to year. Especially for mothers who are too young to be giving birth (under the age of 20), they can do prevention by participating in this KB program. According to Indonesia’s Ministry of Health (2017), KB program also aims to increase the family quality, so

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there can be sense of security, peace, and goals towards a better life and understanding the wellness and happiness of the soul[8].

Indonesia has many different methods of contraception or KB methods that can be used for couples of childbearing age. There are Modern KB methods such as women sterilization with tubectomy, men sterilization (vasectomy, IUD, implant, injection, pills, condom, and Amenore Lactation Method). There are also Traditional KB such as using medicine or methods like periodic abstinence, interrupted intercourse, and other Traditional KB methods (Kemenkes, 2022)[9]. There are many KB methods that can be used, but to prevent pregnancy permanently people can utilize the KONTAP (Kontrasepsi Mantap) methods, which includes tubectomy and vasectomy[10]. Indonesia's Ministry of Health (2017) states that the most used contraception methods in Indonesia are injection (63,71%), pills (17,24%), IUD (7,35%), implants (7,19%), tubectomy (2,76%), condom (1,24%), and vasectomy (0,50%)[11]. But, according to Surabaya City Health Office data of 2019, vasectomy method is the lowest used methods in Surabaya, where there are 1.592 users or 0,40% of all KB Methods used in Surabaya[12]. According to that data, the aim of this study is to identify the effect of attitude towards behavior on the intention to use vasectomy contraception in men.

2. Methods

This study is a quantitative study with observational analytic study design. The approach used is cross-sectional. This study aims to identify the effect of attitude toward behavior on the intention of using vasectomy contraception in men. This study was conducted in Kelurahan Putat Jaya, Kecamatan Sawahan, Surabaya. This study was conducted from May to June 2022. In this study, the population are men with three or more children that domiciled in Kelurahan Putat Jaya, Kecamatan Sawahan, Surabaya. The sample for this study is 57 men with three or more children. The sample has been previously determined according to the number of couple at childbearing age with three or more children in Kelurahan Putat Jaya using Lemeshow's sample size formula. The sampling method is simple random sampling.

This study observes two variables, independent and dependent variables. The independent variable for this study is attitude towards behavior, meanwhile the dependent variable is vasectomy contraception. The data used in this study is primary data that are collected through interview with men that has three or more children in Kelurahan Putat Jaya, using questionnaire as interview instrument. To determine whether or not the effect exist, the analysis was conducted with Binary Logistic Regression.

3. Results

Table 1 Frequency Distribution of Respondent's Characteristics in Kelurahan Putat Jaya

Characteristic	N	%
Age		
25-30 Years Old	3	5.3
31-40 Years Old	5	8.8
41-50 Years Old	49	86.0
Education		
No Formal Education	1	1.8
SD	17	29.8
SMP	19	33.3
SMA	17	29.8
Perguruan Tinggi	3	5.3
Knowledge		
Low	18	31.6
Moderate	30	52.6
Good	9	15.8

Information		
Low	18	31.6
Moderate	20	35.1
Good	19	33.3
Total	57	100.0

From the table shown above, there are 57 respondents, where the majority of them are 41-50 years old (86%), meanwhile the minority of them are 25-30 years old (5,3%). On the other hand, the majority respondent, 19 respondents in this study has the education level of SMP or Middle School (33,3%), 17 has the education level of SD or Primary School (29,8%), 17 has the education level of SMA or High School (29,8%), 3 respondents has the educational level of Perguruan Tinggi or College (5,3%), and 1 responden hasn't finished any school or has no education (1,8%). Looking at the respondents' knowledge level, there are 30 respondent (52,6%) that are sure about the vasectomy contraception, and then there are 20 respondents (35,1%) that have received information regarding the vasectomy contraception.

Table 2 Frequency Distribution of Respondents Based on Their Attitude Toward Behavior on Men in Childbearing Age in Kelurahan Putat Jaya

Attitude Toward Behavior	N	(%)
Not Supporting	47	82.5
Supporting	10	17.5
Very Supporting	0	0
Total	57	100.0

Attitude toward behavior is a behavioral evaluation of respondents, either positively or negatively, on the usage of vasectomy contraception. According to the table, there are 47 out of 57 respondents (82,5%) that doesn't support the usage of vasectomy for contraception, and there are no respondents who are very supportive towards the usage of vasectomy for contraception.

Table 3 Test Result for the Effect of Attitude Toward Behavior on the Intention to Use Vasectomy Contraception in Men in Kelurahan Putat Jaya

Attitude Toward Behavior	Intention				Total		Logistic Binary Regression		Interpretation
	No Intention		Intention				P-Value	Exp (B)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%			
Not Supporting	37	78.7	10	21.3	47	100.0	Ref.	Ref.	Significant effect
Supporting	1	9.7	9	90.3	10	100.0	0.002	33.3	

From the table show, the majority of the respondents who has no intention on using the vasectomy contraception have "not supporting" attitude toward behavior. To determine the effect between variables, the study uses the Logistic Binary Regression. The result of that test shows that there is a significant effect on those two variables with 0,002 p-value ($<\alpha=0.05$) for "supporting" attitude toward behavior. Therefore, we can conclude that attitude toward behavior in "supporting" category have 33,3 times more effect than "not supporting" category on the intention to use vasectomy contraception.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Effect of Knowledge on Intention to Use Vasectomy Contraception

Attitude towards behavior is a behavior affected by an individual's behavioral beliefs and the evaluation of that behavior[13]. The result of this study shows that there is a significant effect of attitude towards behavior on the intention to use vasectomy contraception. This result is in line with other study done by Satria, that states that 55% of the group using vasectomy contraception has a negative behavior due to the lack of faith on the result of that method[14]. Someone's belief about using vasectomy contraception will give benefit and won't have any side effect. Meanwhile, someone that doesn't have faith on the method will have a negative outcome.

The majority of respondents in this study have a "not supporting" attitude towards behavior in the usage of vasectomy contraception. This "not supporting" attitude towards behavior have a higher chance in effecting someone's intention in using the vasectomy contraception compared to those who has a "supporting" attitude towards behavior. Therefore, if there is not support in an individual, then the intention to use the vasectomy contraception method won't be formed. This result is in line with TPB theory according to Ajzen in Amanda (2017) that states that someone's behavior is based on their belief on the consequence from their action and the strength of their belief on the result of that action[15].

5. Conclusion

Based on the result of this study, we can conclude that there is a significant effect of attitude towards behavior on the intention to use vasectomy contraception in men at childbearing age with more than three children in Kelurahan Putat Jaya, Kecamatan Sawahan, Surabaya. Besides the attitude towards behavior factor, the intention to use contraception can also be affected by other factors as well. From this study, we hope that it can become further reference for other studies in the same field, especially on the usage of vasectomy contraception.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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